

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

D4: Report on the source code implementation of a digital twin model of a transfer standard spectroradiometer, which enables the unit of spectral irradiance to be transferred from the calibration laboratory to end user applications

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
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Glossary

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1 Introduction

Accurate conversion of raw spectroradiometer signals into radiometric and photometric quantities with associated uncertainties is essential for absolute calibrated measurements but remains challenging in practice. Modern array spectrometers output pixel indices and digital counts that must undergo e.g., pixel to wavelength transfer and spectral responsivity correction provided by radiometric characterisations and calibrations, to obtain physically meaningful quantities such as spectral irradiance or illuminance.

Each processing step introduces uncertainties, including detector noise, calibration errors, wavelength inaccuracies, and numerical effects. Although the mathematical transformations are well established, rigorous and traceable uncertainty propagation across the full processing chain is often inconsistent or neglected. The diversity of array spectroradiometer hardware and software including the entrance optics, calibration procedures, and data formats further complicates reproducible and validated analysis. In many applications, uncertainty estimates are oversimplified or omitted, despite being crucial for instrument comparison, conformity assessment, and quantitative modelling. Existing software tools typically focus on visualization or basic calibration and rarely provide transparent, standardized workflows that maintain a complete uncertainty budget.

To address these limitations, an open-source Python-based implementation that converts raw digital spectroradiometer data into radiometric and photometric quantities with comprehensive Monte Carlo-based uncertainty propagation was developed in the 22IEM05 NEWSTAND project. Within this software, corrections and their measurement uncertainties determined during the characterization of the array spectroradiometers are considered. As a result, spectral and spectrally integrated quantities are obtained in physically meaningful units with full measurement uncertainty, enabling array spectroradiometers to be used as transfer standard instruments in spectroradiometry.

The software is written in Python and will be published at the end of the project under the MIT license. The software provides a graphical user interface for ease of use and visualization of every processing step. Different models can be used for the transfer of raw spectroradiometer output into physical quantities. Each model defines the application and the order of radiometric corrections. Radiometric corrections for dark data, non-linearity, straylight, optical bandwidth, spectral responsivity and pixel number to wavelength transfer are available. Figure 1 shows the visual representation of *Model 3* including the order of the applied corrections and the connection between calibration and measurement chain. While the users can define their own models in the source code, three of them are provided and ready to use. The fourth model will be implemented by the end of the project:

- **Model 1:** Includes the before-mentioned radiometric corrections and models the spectral responsivity (SR) with a best-estimate value and a type A measurement uncertainty without wavelength correlations.
- **Model 2:** Extension of model 1, SR data is provided as a Monte Carlo data set allowing to model wavelength correlations.

Figure 1. Model 3 as implemented in the analysis software. It implements two data processing chains to fully propagate wavelength correlations of the spectral responsivity.

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- **Model 3:** Similar to model 2 but SR is calculated separately during each Monte Carlo run using the measured raw data of the calibration (“calibration chain”). Due to the usage of two data chains, calibration and measurements are modelled in a consistent manner.
 - **Model 4:** Extension of model 3. It adds device-correlations between the calibration and the measurement chain. We consider this model as the most accurate in terms of determination of measurement uncertainties.

All models allow to carry out a full Monte Carlo analysis. As a result, spectral data as well as spectrally integrated data is obtained with its corresponding measurement uncertainty.

Within this report, we describe the source code implementation, the graphical user interface and the settings file of the spectrometer which is to be modelled. The software itself is called NEWSTAND App in the following.

2 Software Architecture

The implementation follows an object-oriented (OOP) architecture in Python, structured around two primary abstractions:

- Radiometric Python Objects (RPOs).
- Radiometric Python Models (RPMs).

This design enables flexible composition of radiometric correction steps and supports both calibration and measurement workflows.

2.1 Radiometric Python Object (RPO)

Each correction or processing step in the radiometric chain is encapsulated in an RPO. All RPOs inherit from a common base class, RPOBase, which provides core functionality such as:

- Standardized input/output data handling.
- Metadata management.
- Execution interfaces.
- Measurement uncertainty propagation support.

This abstraction ensures that each radiometric correction step is self-contained, reusable, and interchangeable.

2.2 Radiometric Python Model (RPM)

An RPM represents a full radiometric model composed of multiple RPOs. All RPMs inherit from the RPMBase class. The primary responsibilities of RPMBase include:

- Managing collections of RPO instances.
- Executing RPOs in a predefined sequential order.
- Handling data transfer between RPOs.
- Providing a unified interface for model execution.

The modular nature of RPMs allows users / developers to construct complex processing pipelines by combining simple building blocks.

2.3 Calibration and Measurement Chains

A key feature of the implementation is the separation of the processing workflow into two distinct chains:

- Calibration chain.
- Measurement chain.

Each chain consists of an ordered list of RPOs. This separation enables accurate modeling of device correlations, ensuring that calibration-derived measurement uncertainties and corrections are properly propagated into measurement results.

The RPMBase class manages both chains and ensures consistent data flow across them.

2.4 Data Handling and Execution Flow

Data handling is centralized within the RPMBase class. Input data is passed sequentially from one RPO to the next, allowing each processing step to modify or augment the dataset.

Key characteristics of the execution flow include:

- Sequential processing of RPO lists.
- Transparent data propagation.
- Consistent handling of metadata and uncertainties.

This approach minimizes redundancy and simplifies debugging and validation.

2.5 Measurement Uncertainty Propagation and Monte Carlo Simulation

A central feature of the implementation is its comprehensive treatment of measurement uncertainty (MU). Each RPO supports two modes of operation:

1. Best estimate mode.
2. Monte Carlo simulation mode.

In best estimate mode, deterministic values are propagated through the processing chain. In contrast, Monte Carlo mode enables stochastic propagation of uncertainties by drawing random samples from defined input distributions.

In Monte Carlo mode, each input quantity can be represented by a probability distribution rather than a single value. During execution:

- Random samples are generated for all inputs with a measurement uncertainty.
- Each RPO processes these samples consistently.
- Output distributions are obtained after propagating samples through the full chain.

This allows the metrological digital twin to approximate the full probability density function of the measurement result.

A key strength of the framework is the ability to model different types of uncertainty contributions explicitly. These include, but are not limited to:

- Instrumental uncertainties (e.g., detector noise, non-linearity).
- Calibration uncertainties (e.g., reference standards, transfer errors).

-
- Environmental influences (e.g., temperature effects).
 - Model uncertainties (e.g., approximations in physical corrections).

Each contribution can be implemented within individual RPOs, allowing uncertainties to be introduced exactly at the stage where they physically occur. This ensures a realistic and traceable measurement uncertainty budget.

2.6 Correlation Handling

By separating calibration and measurement chains, correlations between quantities can be preserved. For example:

- Calibration-derived uncertainties can be reused in the measurement chain.
- Shared parameters can maintain statistical dependence.

This is particularly important for transfer standard instruments, where calibration and measurement processes are intrinsically linked. For example, non-linearities of the spectrometer are equal during calibration and during measurement.

2.7 Advantages of the Approach

The Monte Carlo-based uncertainty propagation provides several advantages:

- Full non-linear propagation of uncertainties.
- Natural handling of complex and non-Gaussian distributions.
- Direct estimation of confidence intervals.
- Compatibility with the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM Supplement 1).

Uncertainty contributions introduced at any stage are automatically propagated to subsequent steps without additional implementation effort.

2.8 Graphical User Interface Integration

The implementation is designed to operate independently of the GUI while remaining fully compatible with it. The GUI is developed using the Qt framework.

Key GUI features include:

- Visualization of the RPO list within an RPM.
- Interactive selection of individual RPOs.
- Access to detailed information, including:
 - Input and output data.
 - Physical modeling descriptions.
 - Intermediate results.

This tight integration enhances transparency and usability, particularly for debugging, educational and scientific purposes.

2.9 Extensibility and Maintainability

The use of inheritance for both RPOs and RPMs ensures a high degree of extensibility:

- New correction steps can be added by subclassing RPOBase.
- New models can be created by subclassing RPMBase.
- Existing components can be easily replaced or reconfigured.

This design supports rapid prototyping and testing of alternative radiometric models without modifying the core framework.

2.10 Interchangeability and Modularity

RPOs and RPMs are designed to be interchangeable due to their shared base classes. This enables:

- Plug-and-play model construction.
- Easy comparison of different modeling approaches.
- Reusability of components across multiple applications.

Such modularity is particularly valuable in research and calibration environments where models evolve over time.

2.11 Licensing and Compatibility

All software packages used in the implementation are compatible with the MIT license. This ensures:

- Open and permissive use of the codebase.
- Ease of distribution and collaboration.
- Compatibility with both academic and industrial applications.

3 The Graphical User Interface

The graphical user interface is shown in Figure 2. The user interface is structured into three sections:

- The left part defines the user input via the selection of the spectrometer model, the measurement and calibration files. It also contains a list of the RPOs within the calibration and the measurement chain. On the lower left sides different settings for the Monte Carlo simulation can be defined, the best-estimate and the Monte Carlo model can be run and results can be saved to a file.
- The middle part contains the resulting graphical representation of the results and, when available, the input files are shown.
- On the right part, log messages provide detailed information on the progress and error messages about missing or not correctly formatted files.

The NEWSTAND App expects three input files. The modelling of a spectrometer is specified in a spectrometer settings file. Measurement data must include a light data file and a dark data file. The files are selected via the three buttons in the upper left in the sections “Spectrometer” and “Measurement”, see **Figure 2**. Underneath the buttons a label depicts the currently applied model as specified in the spectrometer settings file. A list of the corrections selected for modelling follows, see **Figure 3**. If a file was not found or couldn't be loaded correctly, the background color changes to red. Each item of the list is selectable. Upon selection, the App changes the central tab to the “Radiometric Object” tab. On the right side of the middle section, a description of the object is given in a text box on the left which displays additional information on the applied model and the required input data. If the model has been run (see next paragraph), the input and output data of the object is shown in the graph as well as the relative change from input to output data due to the applied correction.

Figure 2. User Interface of the NEWSTAND App.

For x-y data (For example pixel-signal for the light or dark object) the additional “Visualize Input Data” can be selected to inspect the raw input data.

The list is followed by buttons that execute the model (see **Figure 4**), either in a single run or in a Monte Carlo simulation. The single run button applies the model to get a best estimate without uncertainties or correlating the corrections. The main purpose is to check if the input data is valid and the applied corrections work as expected. After a successful run, the result can be saved with the respective button. The software creates a “*.txt” result file in the same format as the input data and creates a png image file with the same name displaying the graph on the results file tab.

On the lower left part settings for the Monte Carlo Simulation can be defined (see **Figure 4**). The Monte Carlo simulation is only enabled after a successful single run. The number of Monte Carlo runs is adjustable. The App is currently not speed optimized and does not use several cores for the Monte Carlo analysis. Depending on your machine and the radiometric model used, the simulation may take a while when going to number of runs higher than 10000.

The settings for the confidence interval are used for plotting of the results and the export via the “save MC result” button. The saving routine exports the Monte Carlo results with respective uncertainties in a “.txt” file and the graph displayed on the Monte Carlo Tab as a png image file.

Figure 3. List of the corrections applied in the model.

Figure 4. Running the model and the Monte Carlo simulation

The middle part of the app is used to plot all the acquired data, either the raw input data or the data generated by the analysis. There are in general 3 tabs. The first “Radiometric Object” tab displays the data transformation by each applied correction step (see **Figure 5**). The relative change employed by the correction is shown as well.

If raw input data is available, a second tab “Visualize Input Data” is created to display the raw data. The raw input data has to be in x-y data format or in a matrix format. If for example polynomial coefficients are supplied by the input data, they cannot be shown in this tab.

shows the visualization of a straylight matrix.

Figure 5. The “Radiometric Object” tab shows the transformation by the correction selected in the list.

Figure 6. The “Visualize Input Data” tab shows a visual representation of the input data of the selected object selected in the list (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). A heatmap to represent a straylight matrix is currently displayed.

The “Result” tab displays the result of the Single model run without any uncertainties. The final “Monte Carlo Simulation” tab shows the result of the Monte Carlo analysis, see

Figure 7. The mean spectral irradiance (best estimate) is shown as well as the last result of the simulation. Additionally, the uncertainty of the x- and y- axis are shown.

At each point you can save and clear the currently displayed graph using the corresponding buttons at the bottom. A crosshair is implemented on the Monte Carlo Simulation graph which reads out the current mouse position in the graph. The coordinates are shown below the "Save MC Result" Button (see **Figure 4**). On a left click, the movement of the crosshair is frozen for a precise readout. Only for the Monte Carlo Simulation Graph: You can check/uncheck the box at the bottom to show the uncertainty in relative or absolute values.

Figure 7. The Monte Carlo Simulation Tab shows the result of the Monte Carlo Analysis. The red graph is the mean spectral irradiance, averaged over all runs. Green shows the uncertainty of the spectral irradiance and blue the uncertainty in wavelength. In the displayed case the wavelength error is extrapolated to an error in spectral irradiance.

4 Modeling the spectrometer:

Four different models are available in the NEWSTAND App, enabling different levels of correlation. The same corrections are available for each model, i.e. dark data correction (necessary), linearity, straylight, bandwidth, pixel to wavelength assignment and spectral irradiance calculation from the spectral responsivity. Depending on the model, the spectral responsivity is applied differently. They are defined in radiometric model settings file.

4.1 The radiometric model settings file

The applied radiometric corrections are defined in the radiometric model settings file (RMS file). It contains different sections marked by square brackets. Different options are available in each section using key-value pairs. The sections are separated into the applied corrections, e.g. [Linearity] or [Bandwidth] (see screenshot in **Figure 8**). Typically, two options need to be defined. The first option refers to the model (= RPO) that will be applied. The different option will be defined later in this section. The second option defines the file that will be used for the modelling giving the required calibration data for the spectrometer. The calibration files need to be stored in the same folder as the radiometric model settings file!

Correction can be disabled by choosing value "None" for the modelling option. The order of the applied corrections is not affected by the order of the RMS file.

There are several examples provided with the NEWSTAND App that can be used as guidelines for users to create their own files.

The following sections are defined and readable:

- [General]
- [Model]
- [Linearity]
- [Straylight]
- [Bandwidth]
- [Pixel to Wavelength]
- [SR*]
- [Interpolation Model]

It is important that the sections and options are written correctly. The read-out is very strict.

4.2 Available corrections and corresponding models

There are different approaches on how to physically model the corrections. The NEWSTAND App has at least two different approaches for most of the corrections. The available models are described briefly in the next paragraphs. Appropriate uncertainties need to be defined for the measurement uncertainty analysis using Monte Carlo simulations.

Linearity

The linearity is corrected using a single n^{th} -order polynomial for all integration times or by using a 2^{nd} -order polynomial with n different polynomials depending on integration time. The coefficients of the polynomials are fully correlated. The correlation is defined by correlation matrices.

Straylight

The straylight can be either corrected using a Zong straylight matrix or by using the longpass filter method (still under development). For uncertainty calculations, the Zong matrix approach uses one uncertainty value for the whole matrix.

```

[General]
# In this section the Model is defined which will be used for analysis
# You can add additional data of your setup, spectrometer, etc. although it is currently not read by the
# App and is just for user information purposes
Model = Newstand1
Spectrometer name = Synthetic1
Serial number = Synthetic1_xxx_xxx

[Linearity]
# Choose linearity correction using single polynomial (SinglePol) or multiple polynomials (MultiPol)
Linearity_Model = SinglePol
File = Synthetic1_linearitytime.txt

[Straylight]
# Choose straylight correction using matrix method (Matrix) and longpass filter method (LPF)
Straylight_Model = Matrix
File = Synthetic1_straylightmatrix.txt

[Bandwidth]
# Choose bandwidth correction using the Woolliams method (BwWoolliams) or Schinke/triangular method (BwTriangular)
Bandwidth_Model = BwTriangular
File = Synthetic1_bandwidth.txt

[Pixel to Wavelength]
# Choose pixel to wavelength assignment using one polynom(SinglePol),
# multiple polynomials (MultiPol) or emission line model (EmissionlineModel)
# for the pixel to wavelength assignment
PXTowl_Model = SinglePol
File = Synthetic1_pxtowavelength.txt

[SR_singlefile]
# Choose the correct SR settings according to the model
# For <Newstand1> set the section as <SR_singlefile> and add the option <File> with the name of the corresponding .txt file
# For <Newstand2> set the section as <SR_mcfiles> and add the option <spectralresponsivity_mc_data_path> with name of the corresponding zip file
# For <Newstand3> set the section as <SR_calibrationchain>
# Two options <Calchain_light_file> and <Calchain_dark_file> with the names of the files of the corresponding calibration data
# and <spectralresponsivity_mc_data_path> with a zip file containing the spectral irradiance corresponding to the calibration data file
File = Synthetic1_spectralresponsivity.txt

[Interpolation Model]
Interpolation = yes
x_start = 300
x_stop = 1035
x_delta = 1

```

Figure 8. Screenshot of the radiometric model settings file that defines the modelling of the metrological digital twin.

Bandwidth

Two models are available. The first model uses a triangular correction with a defined bandwidth and pixel spacing. The second model uses the Woolliams correction with a linear correction around each pixel. The uncertainty of the coefficients for the linear corrections is defined as standard deviation.

Pixel to wavelength

The pixel to wavelength assignment can be done in two different ways. Either provide a single polynomial of n^{th} order or the raw emission lines. A third experimental model is also available using a 4^{th} order polynomial with additional transfer functions. The single polynomial method and the 4^{th} order polynomial are correlated by standard deviation and correlation coefficients or by a correlation matrix.

Spectral Responsivity

The spectral responsivity is applied differently depending on the used model. Refer to the summary and **Figure 1**.

Interpolation Model

Interpolates the error in wavelength to an error in spectral irradiance. You need to specify if you want to use the interpolation and set the wavelength interval where you want to interpolate and set the step size.

5 Conclusion

The presented implementation provides a robust and flexible framework for modeling a metrological digital twin of a transfer standard spectroradiometer. Its object-oriented design, combined with strong support for measurement uncertainty propagation and GUI integration, makes it well-suited for both research and operational use.

The separation into RPOs and RPMs, along with the dual calibration and measurement chains, enables accurate and transparent modeling of radiometric processes. The extensible architecture ensures that the framework can evolve alongside advances in measurement science and instrumentation.